

Synthesis of 3-Aryl 2-Phenylimino 4-Thiazolidones and Their 1,1-Dioxide

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Some 3-aryl 2-arylimino 4-thiazolidones and their 1, 1-dioxides have been synthesised by the cyclisation of unsymmetrical thiourea and monochloro acetic acid with a view to studying their biological activity.

Organic compounds containing sulphur as sulphathiazole, thiazole, thiadiazole and mercaptobenzothiazole have been shown to possess bacteriostatic¹, antifungal², antitubercular action^{3,4}. On this basis a systematic study of mixed thiazolidones of the type (I) were considered to be of interest as they themselves and their derivatives are of therapeutic importance. In view of the pharmacological importance⁵ of 1,1-dioxides of thiazolidones, it was also worthwhile to synthesise such compounds. The mixed thiazolidones were prepared by the cyclization of unsymmetrical thioureas with monochloro acetic acid in presence of fused sodium acetate or pyridine in ethanolic medium. The structure of thiazolidones were confirmed by the acid hydrolysis. The resemblance in m.p. and analysis of diones obtained by hydrolysis of symmetrical and unsymmetrical thiazolidones confirmed the structure. 3-Aryl-2-phenylimino -4-thiazolidones were converted into corresponding 1,1-dioxide⁶ (II) by oxidation with acidic potassium permanganate solution in presence of sodium bisulphite.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-(o)-Tolyl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone : 1-Phenyl 3-(o) tolyl thiourea (3.0 gm, .012 mole), and monochloroacetic acid (1.5 gm, .012 mole) were refluxed with fused sodium acetate (1.3 g.) in presence of ethanol (10 ml.) on water bath for 4-5 hr. The resultant mixture was poured into the ice cold water. A precipitate was obtained which was filtered and washed several times with hot water, yield (1.8 gm.), 74%. Crystallisation of the crude product from ethanol afforded analytical sample m.p. 120°. Found : N, 10.0; S, 11.6; C₁₆H₁₄N₂OS requires N, 9.93; S, 11.3%.

Other unsymmetrical thiazolidones were prepared similarly and their analytical data and m.p. are recorded in the Table I.

TABLE I
3-Aryl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone (I)

S.No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% N		% S	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	120	74	10.1	9.93	11.6	11.31
2.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	150	68	9.8	9.93	11.2	11.31
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	80	60	10.0	9.93	11.5	11.31
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	149	75	9.5	9.22	10.7	10.57
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	140	72	9.3	9.22	10.4	10.57
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	185	65	9.0	9.22	10.6	10.57
7.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	174	68	8.2	8.07	9.5	9.22
8.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	109	60	7.3	7.10	8.4	8.12
9.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	93	63	9.3	9.39	10.4	10.73
10.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	151	75	9.6	9.39	10.3	10.73
11.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	80	81	9.2	9.39	10.6	10.73
*12.	<i>o</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	147	63	8.2	8.03	9.3	9.28
*13.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	157	68	8.4	8.03	9.5	9.18

* The free bases were gummy mass which were solidified by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas into the ethereal solution, the m.p. and analysis recorded in the Table I are of hydrochloride of the free bases.

3-(*o*-)Tolyl-2-phenylimino 4-thiazolidone 1,1-dioxide : 3-(*o*-) Tolyl 2-phenylimino 4-thiazolidone (1.0 g., .0035 mole), was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.). The resultant solution was treated with 3% aqueous solution of potassium permanganate with constant

TABLE II
3-Aryl-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone 1,1-dioxides (II)

S.No.	Nature of aryl group R	M.P. °C	Yield %	% N		% S	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	90	54	8.6	8.91	10.2	10.19
2.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	153	50	9.1	8.91	10.5	10.19
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	85	60	9.3	8.91	10.3	10.19
4.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	87	62	8.6	8.48	9.9	9.69
5.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	159	65	8.2	8.48	9.5	9.69
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	82	55	8.5	8.48	9.8	9.69

stirring at 30–40° for half an hour. An aqueous solution of sodiumbisulphite was added to it till solution became colourless and again stirred for another half an hour, then water added and left overnight. A semi-solid mass was obtained which was crystallised from ethanol, yield (0.6 gm.) 54% m.p. 90°. Found : N, 8.6; S, 10.2; C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₃S requires N, 8.91; S, 10.09%.

The analytical data, m.p. of derivatives of other 3-aryl 2-phenylimine 4-thiazolidone 1,1-dioxides are shown in Table II.

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